

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AMEZAH****FIRST NAME: ISAAC NEWTON****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used Microsoft 365 on Windows 10 Pro

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the primary method recommended in the ACA-401D Coursepack for avoiding plagiarism in academic writing?
 - Paraphrasing without citation.
 - Citing all sources used in the research.¹**
 - Using common knowledge without attribution.
 - Quoting extensively from primary sources.

2. What is a key difference between American and British English regarding spelling, as discussed in the Coursepack?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401D/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 34.

- Use of “color” vs. “colour”.
 - Use of “theater” vs. “theatre”.
 - Use of “organise” vs. “organize”.
 - All of the above.**²
3. What is the primary purpose of the dissertation prospectus in the research process?
- To summarise the findings of the dissertation.
 - To provide a complete plan for executing the dissertation.**³
 - To present the final manuscript for publication.
 - To outline the limitations of the study.
4. Which of the following best describes a potential source of researcher bias in dissertation research?
- The use of a standardised questionnaire.
 - The selection of research questions is based on personal interest.**⁴
 - Collaboration with multiple researchers.
 - Adhering to ethical research guidelines.
5. According to the European Commission Style Guide, what is the correct spacing rule for punctuation marks in English?

² Ibid., 25.

³ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research (Second Edition)* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 4.

⁴ Ibid., 8.

- A double space should follow punctuation marks.
 - Punctuation marks should be close to the preceding word, letter, or number.**⁵
 - A hard space should always separate punctuation marks.
 - Punctuation marks should be followed by a single space only at the end of a sentence.
6. According to the European Commission Style Guide, which of the following statements about title capitalisation is correct?
- All major words in titles should be capitalised.
 - Only the first word and proper nouns in titles should be capitalised.**⁶
 - Titles should always be written in lowercase to maintain consistency.
 - Titles should be capitalised according to the American style of capitalisation.
7. What is the primary purpose of the literature review in a dissertation?
- To summarise all existing research on the topic.
 - To provide a comprehensive bibliography for the dissertation.
 - To identify gaps in the literature and situate the study.**⁷
 - To make an argument for the importance of the research problem.

⁵ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth Edition (European Commission, 2021), 8.

⁶ Ibid., 23.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 146.

8. What is the primary purpose of a research problem in a qualitative dissertation?
- To test a hypothesis.
 - To describe and interpret phenomena.
 - To identify and define the research problem.⁸**
 - To measure variables.
9. Which of the following is NOT a reason for citing sources, according to Turabian?
- To give credit to original authors.
 - To avoid plagiarism.
 - To increase the length of the paper.⁹**
 - To provide a pathway for readers to verify information.
10. What is a critical component of constructing a research argument outlined in Turabian's manual?
- Relying solely on personal opinions.
 - Assembling evidence based on readers' questions.¹⁰**
 - Avoiding engagement with sources.
 - Presenting unverified claims.

⁸ Ibid., 89.

⁹ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 138.

¹⁰ Ibid., 56.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.